

FEATURES OF TEACHING THE DISCIPLINE “RUSSIAN LANGUAGE” TO ECONOMICS STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The features of working with economics students, especially the direction of banking, are described; the basic principles of selection and development of material in the conditions of studying the specialty and orientation of the university are analyzed.

The main objective of the “Russian Language” course within the framework of university teaching is the formation of the professional language competence of a specialist, in our case, economics students studying at a mechanical engineering university. Our students are future specialists in a very important area of public life, who will develop the economy of individual enterprises, and possibly the country as a whole. Accordingly, when working with economics students, it is necessary to take into account a number of factors: the characteristics of the specialty, the technical focus of the university, teaching conditions (shortage of hours), the capabilities of modern technology (the presence of spell checking built into text editors). Due to these factors, special attention should be paid to the development of text production skills, both written and oral. The focus of teachers on identifying learning goals, selecting educational material and developing new methods for presenting this material helps to achieve maximum effect in a fairly short time.

Economic culture is a system of formal and informal rules and norms of behavior, customs and traditions, individual and new interests, characteristics of employee behavior, leadership style in organizational structures at various levels.

Economic culture is of great importance in shaping the economic policy of production and economic structures at any level, since shortcomings contribute to an increase in the costs of production of products and services, their increase in the process of distribution and sales and, thereby, rising prices, the emergence of artificial shortages, overstocking, etc. etc. In addition, they often lead to the defeat of enterprises entering international markets due to ignorance of the cultural environment of business partners and the inability to carry out transactions.

These circumstances significantly modify the requirements for economic training of the entire contingent of specialists: entrepreneurs, managers, economists, marketers, etc., causing the need to expand and change the disciplines studied in the relevant specialties, including the discipline "Russian language".

The borrowing of modern market terminology, the activation of historicisms, and active semantic processes in the vocabulary lead to the emergence of new concepts that characterize various aspects of market relations. Special attention is paid to them in professional Russian language classes.

For students of economic specialties, due to the extensive vocabulary of economic vocabulary in the Russian language, it is necessary to learn to use this vocabulary, develop both written and oral skills while simultaneously increasing the level of economic culture.

To increase the efficiency of studying the professional Russian language by fully assimilating the material, the author suggests ways to increase the level of economic culture:

✓ In the public consciousness, there has been a liberalization of the concept of language norms, norms of speech culture, as a result of which the range of deviations from language norms allowed by public opinion has significantly expanded. This necessitates the need to take measures to support language norms and norms of speech culture.

In this regard, the norms for placing stress in economic terms are especially important for the cultural speech of a modern specialist in terms of studying economic vocabulary. Economic vocabulary is subject to the same accentological laws as general literary vocabulary. It contains many borrowed words that cause difficulties in pronunciation. Some forms have an accent that performs a semantic-distinguishing function, that is, the meaning of words differs with emphasis, for example, "credit - credit." Both are of Latin origin. The form "kredit" in the meaning of "loan", "debt" was always used without changes, and the form "kredit" (translated from Latin "he believes") represents the right side of the accounting accounts, which reflects the expenditure side, where All expenses are recorded on this account.

The norm is the emphasis on "wholesale", that is, in large quantities, in large quantities. The "wholesale" option is colloquial. Based on the meaning of this term, that is, in large quantities, the common expression "small wholesale" is incorrect, since it turns out to be nonsense - "in small large quantities." This happens due to ignorance of the exact meaning of the word, as in the expressions "price list", "inspection check", "favorite hobby".

For a number of reasons, the emphasis in the word "marketing" fluctuates. The term denotes the philosophy of modern business, which determines the strategy and tactics of a company in a competitive environment. The variant of stress on the first syllable - "ma'rketing" - corresponds to the stress in the source language - English. The form "marketing" is a variant adapted to the accentological structure of the Russian language. Currently, "marketing" is used in professional economic speech, which is more academic, and "marketing" in colloquial speech. The above examples show that the rules for setting stress are quite complex, but mastering them is necessary for competent mastery of speech and increasing the general level of culture of the speaker and his professional rating.

✓ Nowadays, economic terminology has gone beyond professional communication. Its use is updated in various communicative situations and corresponding types and genres of speech. Therefore, to increase the level of economic culture, it is necessary to master economic vocabulary in oral conversation. For example, when conducting business games in professional

Russian language classes, students actively use a variety of economic vocabulary, which allows them to fully reveal the functions of economic vocabulary and increase their learning of the material.

FUNCTIONS OF ECONOMIC VOCABULARY OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN ORAL CONVERSATION:

NOMINATIVE FUNCTION. If you add all the shoes sewn to all the oil produced in our country, count it all and add the revenue from dry cleaners - that's your GDP. In this example, there is a despecialization of the term;

EXPRESSIVE FUNCTION. The legalization of mental speculative activity led to its active development. The term to speculate has been determined and used in the meaning: to strive to benefit from intellectual activity;

THE FUNCTION OF INCREASING THE SOCIAL PRESTIGE OF THE STATEMENT. The devaluation of cultural and moral values is the main cause of the global financial and economic crisis. The term "devaluation" has been determinologized and is used to emphasize the significance of the statement in the meaning: devaluation.

All this indicates the interaction of linguistic units of living spoken speech and literary and written language, as a result of which a change in the culture of both oral and written speech occurs, and at the junction of such interaction, the economic vocabulary of the Russian language continues to develop and actively influence the level of economic culture of students.

In conclusion, we can conclude that studying the economic vocabulary of the Russian language is a necessary link in mastering the language of the specialty, in improving the speech culture of a modern specialist in the field of economics. Such ways of increasing the level of economic culture as supporting language norms and norms of speech culture, as well as mastering economic vocabulary in oral conversation, increase the effectiveness of learning the professional Russian language. Correct and appropriate use of economic vocabulary gives

competence and literacy to speech. The study of the Russian language when training specialists should always be accompanied by consideration of active lexical processes; only in this way is it possible to develop speech competencies and achieve a high level of proficiency in the language of the specialty.

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